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Yuldashev Javoxir Abduraxim o'g'liNamangan davlat pedagogika instituti dotsenti,
pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)**BO'LAJAK TARIX O'QITUVCHILARINI AKSILOGIK POZISIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING
IJTIMOIY-PEDAGOGIK ZARURIYATI**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11091485>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada qadriyatlar xaqida tushuncha, uning bugungi kunda dolzarbligi, talabalarda aksiologik dunyoqarashni rivojlantirishda tarix darslarining o'ziga xos o'rni va vazifalari xaqida yoritiladi

Kalit so'zlar: aksiologiya, talaba, vazifa, rivojlantirish, millat, dunyoqarash

Jahon ta'lim maydoniga kirishga yo'naltirilgan yangi ta'lim tizimini shakllantirish sharoitida milliy ta'lim va tarbiyaning ma'naviy-axloqiy va madaniy-tarixiy an'alarini saqlab qolishga imkon beruvchi ta'lim modellarini izlashning faol jarayoni ketmoqda.

Zamonaviy ijtimoiy-madaniy sharoitda umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish muammosi dolzarb xarakterga ega bo'lmoqda, chunki qadriyatlar ta'lim mazmunining asosidir. Insonga hayotning mazmuni haqidagi tushunchalarni qaytarish, o'z shaxsining qaytarilmas - noyobligiga ishonishi, kelajakdagi quvonch va qiyinchiliklarni munosib kutib olishga va o'zini takomillashtirishga tayyorlikka o'rgatish - bugungi kunda ta'lim oldida turgan vazifalardandir.

O'zbekiston fuqarosida madaniyatni qadrllovchi va uning himoyachisini tarbiyalash har bir ta'lim maskani, jamiyatning ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasining asosi bo'lib, uning maqsadi yoshlarda eng yuksak ma'naviy qadriyatlarni: halollik, adolat, mehr-oqibat, erkinlik, bag'rikenglikni, mas'uliyat bilan singdirishdan iboratdir. Zamonaviy vaziyat jamiyatning har bir a'zosi uchun o'z taqdiri uchun, qadriyatlar va qadriyat yo'nalishlarining muayyan tizimini tanlash uchun mas'uliyatni o'z zimmasiga olishni talab qiladi. Qadriyatlarga murojaat qilish zamonamizning asosiy farqlovchi xususiyati, ta'lim sohasidagi davlat siyosatining eng muhim tamoyilidir. So'nggi yillarda ta'limda avlodlarning tarixiy davomiyligiga asoslangan, davlatimiz

an'alarini saqlab qoladigan va rivojlantiradigan qadriyatlar tizimini shakllantirish vazifasi turibdi.

Shaxsning qadriyatlari va qadriyat yo'nalishlari har doim film-fanning turli sohalaridagi olimlarning diqqatini o'ziga jalb etib kelgan. Aksiologiya (yunonch. axios - qimmat, qadr va logos-so'z, tushuncha), yoki qadriyatlar nazariyasi, falsafiy tadqiqotlar nisbatan so'nggi yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanib, XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmi va XX boshida neokant Baden maktabiga tegishli nemis faylasuflari Rudolf German Lotse, Vilgelm Vindelband i Genrix Rikkert asarlarida aks etgan.

Ammo qadriyatlar mavzusi ko'hna va navqiron Sharq, uning tarkibiy qismi bo'lgan Markaziy Osiyo va O'zbekiston mutafakkirlari hamda olimlari uchun ham begona emas! Qadriyatshunoslik tarixining eng teran jihatlarini faqat G'arbdan emas, balki Sharqdan qidirish ham foydadan holi bo'lmas kerak. Xorazmiy, Forobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Najmiddin Kubro, al-Buxoriy, at-Termiziy, Yassaviy, Ulug'bek, Jamiy, Navoiy, Mashrab, Bedil, Maxtumquli, Abay, Behbudiy, A.Avloniy kabimutafakkir va olimlarning ijodida ham bu mavzuning izlari bor. Gap ana shu izlarni izlab topishda, ularni unutmashlikda, yangilab turishda, zamonada realliklari nuqtai nazaridan xolisona talqin qilishdadir.

G'arb qadriyatshunosligida sub'yektiv jihatlariga ko'proq e'tibor beradigan aksiologlar ham bor. Ular qadriyatlarining vujudga kelishini inson, uning sifatleri va faoliyati bilan bog'laydi. Bu oqimga xos qa-

rashlar mashhur sofizm ta'limotiga borib taqaladi. Uni U.Jeyms, J.Dyui (1859-1952), A.Meynong (1873-1920), A.Bergson (1879-1961) kabi ko'zga ko'ringan namoyandalari bor, bu yo'nalish borasida D.Perri, G.Murrey, E.Tolmen, E.Fromm, R.Uilyams kabi olimlar va tadqiqotchilar ish olib borganlar. Ularning g'oyalari G'arb mamlakatlarida keng tarqalgan. Masalan, XX asrning boshlarida U.Jeyms qarashlari, keyinchalik Jon Dyui g'oyalari keng yoyilgan va G'arb madaniyatining barcha sohalariga juda katta ta'sir ko'rsatgan.

G'arb olimlari orasida V.Diltey, X.Erenfels, O.Shpengler, A.Toynbi, P.Sorokin-larni alohida ta'kidlash lozim. Bu olimlar nazarida qadriyatlarni mavhum emas, balki aniq tahlil qilmoq kerak. Ana shunda ularning kelib chiqishi, mohiyati va namoyon bo'lish shakllarini aniqlash oson bo'ladi. Bu diqqatga sazovor fikr bo'lib, undan hozirgi zamon qadriyatshunoslari ijodiy foydalanmoqdalar. Bizning fikrimizcha, qadriyatshu-noslik muammolarini tahlil etish borasidagi qarashlarni hisobga olib, bu oqim vakillarini «plyuralistik aksiologiya» tarafdorlari, deb atash mumkin. Ular qadriyatlarni bir tomondan, voqelik shakllarining mohiyati, ahamiyati, ikkinchi tomondan, shaxs kechinmalari, tuyg'u va xususiyatlari bilan bog'laydilar.

Qadriyatshunoslik asosan qadriyatlar, ularning namoyon bo'lish shakllari, qadrlash xissi, qadrlash tuyg'usi, realikka qadriyatli munosabat va aksiologik yondashuv, ijtimoiy taraqqiyot jarayonida qadriyatlar sohasidagi o'zgarishlar, qadrlash va qadrsizlanish muammolari, tarixni aksiologik tushunish, qadriyat tizimlarining amal qilish xususiyatlari to'g'risidagi masalalarni o'rganadi.

Tarixni o'rganish ma'naviy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish va yosh avlodni tarbiyalashga katta hissa qo'shadi deb o'ylaymiz. Tarix kurslari "vatanparvar", "burch", "fuqaro" kabi tushunchalarining paydo bo'lishi va rivojlanishi jarayonini umumiy va milliy tarixiy materiallardan foydalanib kuzatishga imkon beradi. Shu bilan birga, talabalar turli xil xalqlar

uchun turli davrlarda ushbu tushunchalarning mohiyati va haqiqiy mazmunini eng aniq ochib beradigan aniq vaziyatlar, voqealar va nomlar bilan tanishadilar. Shunday qilib, tarixiylik, konsepsiyalarning o'zi evolyusiyasi to'g'risida prinsipial muhim g'oya yaratiladi.

O.G'aybullayev fikricha, "hozirgi zamon-da yashayotgan yoshlarning ongiga Vatanni sevish, umuminsoniy axloqiy-ma'naviy qadriyatlarni singdirish, milliy o'zligini anglatish; mehr-shafqatli, vijdonli, andishali qilib tarbiyalash" da milliy ong va uning asosiy tarkibiy elementlari bo'lgan tarixiy ong hamda tarixiy xotiraning roli ulkan bo'lib, ular katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Tarix darslarida talabalar Vatanni yaratgan va uning ma'naviy va moddiy boyliklarini oshirgan insonlar taqdiriga hamdardlik bildiradilar. O'quvchilar o'tmish personaji bilan bevosita muloqotga kirishib, u bilan umumlashtiruvchi va farqlovchi tomonlarini, uning o'rnida bo'lishganda qanday yo'l tutishi mumkinligi haqida fikr yuritadilar. Darslik matni va hujjatlar bilan ishlashning istalgan bosqichida quyidagi savollar o'rinlidir: Ushbu voqealarga munosabatingiz qanday? Bu vaziyatda kimni qo'llab-quvvatlar edingiz? Nima uchun, tushuntiring? Sodir bo'lgan tarixiy voqealar materialiga oid bunday savollarga javob berish orqali, talabalar vaziyatlarni tahlil qilish, ishtirokchilar pozitsiyalarini model-lashtirish va ularning rollarini tushunish ko'nikmalarini egallaydilar. Shunday qilib, atrofdagi voqelikda o'z-o'zini aniqlash uchun ayniqsa zarur bo'lgan voqeahodisalarga o'z munosabatini shakllantirish tajribasi to'planadi. Ular o'sha davr tiliga taqlid qilib, o'z asarlarini modellashtirishga taklif etiladi.

Milliy birlik, birdamlik barqaror bo'lgan joydagina milliy davlat, til, madaniyat, qadriyatlar, an'analar yuksalib, milliy maqsadlar va manfaatlar amalga oshishi uchun keng imkoniyatlar yuzaga keladi.

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